

How to Cite (APA): Dinler, D. (2025). An exact method for the uncapacitated single allocation planar hub location problem. In Proceedings of the IMSS'25 (pp. 178–185). Düzce University - Türkiye, 25–27 September 2025.

An Exact Method for the Uncapacitated Single Allocation Planar Hub Location Problem

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KEYWORDS – Hub location problem, planar hub location problem, Nonlinear Programming, Mixed Integer Second Order Cone Programming (MISOCP), single allocation, uncapacitated.

ABSTRACT

Hub-and-spoke networks play a significant role in various fields such as transportation, telecommunications, and supply chain management. In this study, we address the problem of meeting the demand of n given customers (spokes) through p hubs to be located in continuous space. It is assumed that customers must be assigned to a single hub, hub capacities are unlimited, all flows between customers are routed through hubs, hubs are fully connected, and hubs can be positioned anywhere on the plane. The considered problem is formulated as a nonlinear mathematical program which involves products of decision variables and Euclidean distances. Second order cone constraints are employed to accurately represent the Euclidean distances, and a linearization approach is introduced to handle the nonlinearities arising from the products of decision variables. Thus, the problem is efficiently modeled as a Mixed Integer Second Order Cone Programming (MISOCP) formulation. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first exact solution method proposed for the problem even though there are some heuristics. Through computational experiments, the proposed MISOCP is compared with a well-known genetic algorithm from the literature on small sized instances. The results demonstrate that the exact method not only yields optimal solutions in reasonable time, but also outperforms the genetic algorithm in terms of both solution quality and computational time. Furthermore, for a larger 81-node real-life Turkish dataset, a high-quality feasible solution is obtained within 2-hour time limit.

1 INTRODUCTION

Hub-and-spoke networks play a central role in transportation, logistics, telecommunications, and many other fields. In such systems, flow between origin-destination pairs is routed through a set of strategically located hubs, which reduces overall transportation cost and increases network efficiency because of economies of scale ([1], [2]). The hub location problems (HLP) can be mainly categorized into two by considering the locations of hubs: discrete HLP (DHLP) and planar HLP (PHLP).

DHLP has been extensively studied and applied in real-world logistics and telecommunication networks. In DHLP, hubs are restricted to a finite set of candidate locations, and mathematical models are typically formulated as mixed-integer linear programs (MILP), enabling the use of well-

established exact or heuristic solvers [3]. While the discrete assumption simplifies modeling and computation, it can limit practical flexibility in many applications [4]. This motivates the study of continuous-space variants of the problem, where hubs can be located anywhere in the Euclidean plane. Previous approaches to PHLP have relied on heuristic and metaheuristic techniques due to the difficulty of obtaining exact solutions ([4], [5], [6]).

The PHLP version considered in this study assumes each spoke (i.e., demand point) must be assigned to exactly one hub (single allocation), hubs are uncapacitated and fully connected, and all inter-spoke flow is routed through hubs. Although the uncapacitated and single allocation assumptions simplify some aspects, the continuous nature of hub locations and the nonlinear Euclidean distance-based cost terms make the problem computationally challenging. However, advances in Second Order Cone Programming (SOCP) and linearization techniques now offer promising directions for modeling such problems.

This study builds upon these advances by proposing a fully unified, compact, and linearized mathematical formulation which is in the form of Mixed Integer Second Order Cone Programming (MISOCP). The resulting formulation is suitable for exact solutions by modern commercial solvers. The performance of the formulation is tested using the instances of the well-known benchmark dataset in the hub location literature, i.e., Australian Post (AP), and compared with a genetic algorithm from the literature. Preliminary experiments conducted on small problem instances for which optimal solutions are found show the applicability and potential of the MISOCP formulation.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we provide a literature review. Then, we propose an MISOCP formulation for the uncapacitated single allocation PHLP in Section 3. Computational results are presented in Section 4 and Section 5 concludes the study and provides some future research directions.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

DHLP has received significant attention in operations research and logistics optimization. Early foundational work by O’Kelly [1] introduced the DHLP framework and formalized its mathematical underpinnings. Since then, O’Kelly’s models have been extended in various directions, including capacitated variants, multiple allocation settings, and stochastic environments. Notable contributions to the modeling and solution of DHLP have also been made by [2] and [3]. Beyond exact methods, a wide range of heuristic and metaheuristic approaches have been developed for DHLP, such as genetic algorithms [7], variable neighborhood search [8], and simulated annealing [9]. For a comprehensive overview of the DHLP literature, readers are referred to the recent survey presented in [10].

In comparison, PHLP has received relatively limited attention. Assumption of discrete hub locations in DHLP poses a limitation in capturing the spatial distribution of real-world infrastructures like telecommunication or cargo delivery systems. In such infrastructures, hubs (e.g., wireless routers or cargo centers) can be located anywhere in the continuous space. [11] presents a seminal approach to the planar hub location problem using a clustering-based methodology. The method treats nodes as interacting entities in a two-dimensional Euclidean space and formulates the objective as a minimization of squared distances from cluster centroids.

The importance of spatial flexibility in PHLP is also emphasized in [4]. The integration of continuous domains introduced complex nonlinearities in the objective function, especially due to Euclidean distance-based cost metrics. Therefore, authors proposed location-allocation based algorithm. Similarly, [5] introduces a novel hyperbolic smoothing technique to tackle non-differentiable and non-convex objective functions arising in continuous multiple allocation p-hub median problems with uncapacitated hubs. By transforming the model into a differentiable unconstrained optimization problem, the authors enable the use of gradient-based solution methods and report near-optimal results within reasonable computational times.

To improve scalability and adaptability, [6] propose a genetic algorithm-based solution for the uncapacitated single allocation PHLP. Their approach models hubs in continuous space and employ a chromosome structure that encodes both the hub coordinates and allocation patterns. The algorithm balances solution accuracy with computational efficiency.

In this study, we consider the same problem with [6]. For the solution of the problem, we introduce an MISOCP formulation with which the optimal solution can be found. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first modelling paper of the considered problem. Modelling effort is always appreciated as the first stage of optimization process as heuristics do not guarantee to find optimal solutions. Even though they are not efficient in terms of the solution time for the large size problem instances, with developing technology they become more efficient day by day. Also, they can be used in cooperation with heuristic techniques like developing hybrid methods or matheuristics.

3 FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM

In this study, we made the following assumptions. There are n spokes and coordinates of spoke i are given as $a_i = (a_i^1, a_i^2) \in R^2, i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. To serve the spokes p hubs will be located anywhere on the continuous space. Let $y_k = (y_k^1, y_k^2) \in R^2, k \in \{1, \dots, p\}$ is defined as the continuous decision variables for the coordinates of hub p . Hubs are uncapacitated and fully connected to each other. Spokes can be assigned to a single hub and flow between spokes i and j , w_{ij} where $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, can only be made through hubs (i.e., no direct shipping between spokes). Cost components in the problem are collection (spoke to hub), distribution (hub to spoke) and transfer cost (hub to hub) where the latter one is smaller than the former ones because of the economies of scales. We will represent them as α_c, α_d , and α_t , respectively.

Let x_{ik} is the binary decision variable representing the assignment of spoke i to hub k . If the corresponding assignment is done the variable take value 1, otherwise it will be 0. If d_{ik} and d_{kl} represents the Euclidean distances between spoke i and hub k , and hub k and hub l , respectively, the nonlinear formulation of the problem is already given in [6] as follows.

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} (\sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_c \|y_k - a_i\| x_{ik} + \sum_{l=1}^p \alpha_d \|y_l - a_j\| x_{jl} + \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^p \alpha_t \|y_k - y_l\| x_{ik} x_{jl}) \quad (1)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{k=1}^p x_{ik} = 1, \quad \forall i \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ik} \geq 1, \quad \forall k \quad (3)$$

$$x_{ik} \in \{0,1\}, \quad \forall i, k \quad (4)$$

$$y_k = \{y_k^1, y_k^2\} \in R^2, \quad \forall k \quad (5)$$

In the objective function (1), total transportation cost (collection, distribution and transfer costs) is minimized. Constraint (2) guarantees the assignment of each spoke to only one hub. Assignment of at least one spoke to each hub is assured with constraint (3) which results in exactly p hubs. Constraints (4) and (5) are the domain constraints of the decision variables.

There is no effort given to solve this formulation in [6]. In this study, we focused on solving the problem exactly. Thus, we reformulated the problem as an MISOCP. A typical SOCP/MISOCP problem has the following form.

$$\min f^T x \quad (6)$$

Subject to:

$$|A_t x + b_t| \leq c_t^T x + e_t, \quad \forall t \quad (7)$$

where x is the decision vector; A_t is a coefficient matrix; f^T , b_t , and c_t^T are coefficient vectors of appropriate size; and e_t is a scalar. When A_t is matrix of all zeros, the constraint (7) becomes a linear inequality constraint. When all entries are not equal to zero, the constraint (7) is called second order cone constraint. If the decision vector includes some integer variables, then the problem becomes MISOCP. To solve MISOCP problems branch and bounds algorithms are implemented in commercial solvers like Gurobi [12].

In the formulation of PHLP, let d_{ik} and d_{kl} be the Euclidean distance between node i and hub k , and hub k and hub l , respectively. If we add the following constraints to the model, they hold as equality in the optimal solution as we have minimization problem. Note that these constraints are in the form of second order cone constraints.

$$d_{ik} \geq \|y_k - a_i\|, \quad \forall i, k \quad (8)$$

$$d_{kl} \geq \|y_k - y_l\|, \quad \forall k < l \quad (9)$$

In the objective function (1), we have multiplications of decision variables. To linearize these nonlinearities, let us define new variables as $s_{ik} = d_{ik}x_{ik}$, $z_{ikjl} = x_{ik}x_{jl}$, $u_{ikjl} = d_{kl}z_{ikjl}$ and apply Mc-Cormick reformulation [13] by adding the following constraints. With the introduction of these variables, objective function becomes linear.

$$s_{ik} \leq Ux_{ik}, \quad \forall i, k \quad (10)$$

$$s_{ik} \leq d_{ik}, \quad \forall i, k \quad (11)$$

$$s_{ik} \geq d_{ik} - (1 - x_{ik})U, \quad \forall i, k \quad (12)$$

$$z_{ikjl} \geq x_{ik} + x_{jl} - 1, \quad \forall i, j, k, l \quad (13)$$

$$z_{ikjl} \leq x_{ik}, \quad \forall i, j, k, l \quad (14)$$

$$z_{ikjl} \leq x_{jl}, \quad \forall i, j, k, l \quad (15)$$

$$u_{ikjl} \leq Uz_{ikjl}, \quad \forall i, j, k, l \quad (16)$$

$$u_{ikjl} \leq d_{kl}, \quad \forall i, j, k, l \quad (17)$$

$$u_{ikjl} \geq d_{kl} - (1 - z_{ikjl})U, \quad \forall i, j, k, l \quad (18)$$

Constraints (10)-(12) are for the linearization of $d_{ik}x_{ik}$, constraints (13)-(15) are for the linearization of $x_{ik}x_{jl}$ and constraints (16)-(18) are for the linearization of $d_{kl}z_{ikjl}$. In these constraints, U value is a big-M value and its selection affects the efficiency of the solutions. If it is too high, constraints become too loose and solution time increases. If it is selected too low, constraints become too tight and problem may become infeasible. Setting U as the distance between the farthest two spokes in the problem instance is a wise choice (i.e., $U = \max_{i,j} \|a_i - a_j\|$).

The final version of the reformulated MISOCP model presented below. It offers an exact mathematical representation of the PHLP, incorporating both the spatial flexibility of hub locations and the nonlinear cost structure through second order cone and linearized constraints. The nomenclature used in the formulation is summarized in Table A1 in the Appendix. To assess the tractability and effectiveness of the proposed model, we conduct a series of computational experiments and a comparison with existing heuristic methods from the literature in the next section.

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} \left(\sum_{k=1}^p \alpha_c s_{ik} + \sum_{l=1}^p \alpha_d s_{jl} + \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^p \alpha_t u_{ikjl} \right) \quad (19)$$

Subject to:

$$(2) - (5) \text{ and } (8) - (18)$$

$$s_{ik}, d_{ik} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, k \quad (20)$$

$$d_{kl} \geq 0, \quad \forall k, l \quad (21)$$

$$z_{ikjl}, u_{ikjl} \geq 0, \quad \forall i, j, k, l \quad (22)$$

4 COMPUTATIONAL EXPERIMENTS

The experiments have been performed on a computer with 11th generation Intel Core i7 CPU, 2.70 GHz and 16 GB RAM. Solution methods (MISOCP formulation and an algorithm from the literature) are coded in Python employing Gurobi as solver [12].

Among the PHLP studies in literature, we make comparison with the study in [6] as it is already compared with the work of [4]. We skipped the algorithm in [11] as it has distances squares in the objective function. We also ignored the study in [5] since there is a small difference between their study and our assumptions. We force the solution to exactly have given number of hubs but in [5] some of hubs may remain empty and in the final solution less than the given number of hubs can be located. Adding this constraint to the problem prevents the application of the smoothing algorithm they proposed to our case.

In [6], authors proposed a specialized genetic algorithm named PHLGA (Planar Hub Location Genetic Algorithm), which does not guarantee to find optimal solution. This algorithm encodes allocation decisions in vector with size n , in which i^{th} entry shows the hub number to which i^{th} spoke is assigned to. In addition, for the continuous optimization part (hub locations), they used $p \times 2$ matrix in which k^{th} row shows the x and y coordinates of k^{th} hub. After semi-randomly (in a solution, hub locations are randomly generated and then each spoke is assigned to the nearest hub) generating the initial population with size $\min(np, 100)$, each parent (solution) is allowed to generate offsprings (new solutions) with the problem specific crossover operators and also each offspring is mutated with probability 0.2 with the problem specific mutation operators. After each crossover&mutation process, the best solution among parents and offsprings is selected for the next generation. Completion of this process for all the solutions in a generation, the process is repeated with the new population in the next generation. The authors limit the generation number to 300 to stop the algorithm. End of 300 generation means a replication and they perform 5 replications and report the best value among 5 replications. To be able to make a comparison and show the applicability of our MISOCP formulation, we recoded PHLGA algorithm on Python (with the exact parameters they have selected) and ran the experiments on the same computer which is used for MISOCP formulation.

AP dataset is commonly used in hub location literature [3]. The whole dataset includes 200 nodes, we generated problem instances with different sizes ($n=10, 20, 25$) and solve them for different number of hubs. The cost parameters are set as $\alpha_c = 3, \alpha_d = 2, \alpha_t = 0.75$ as in the study by [6]. The preliminary computational results can be seen in Table 1 in which $P_{n,p}$ represents the problem with n nodes and p hubs. In the table, we present the objective function values of both methods (MISOCP formulation proposed in this study and a genetic algorithm from the literature) along with their solution time in seconds. Note that the time of genetic algorithm is the total time of 5 replications to obtain the best objective value reported in the table. In the last column, percent deviations of the heuristic algorithm from the optimal solution are reported. As seen in the table, exact solutions are obtained faster than the heuristic algorithm for small problem instances. When we investigate the objective function values of instance with size 10 for different p values, the performance of the heuristic algorithm tends to degrade as the number of hubs increases. Moreover, the comparison of

$P_{10,2}$, $P_{20,2}$ and $P_{25,2}$ indicates that the heuristic algorithms may increasingly deviate from to optimal solution when the number of nodes grows.

Table 1 Preliminary comparison of MISOCP and study of [6]

Problem instance	MISOCP		Genetic Algorithm in [6]		% Deviation
	Objective	Time (s)	Objective	Time (s)	
$P_{10,2}$	144445915.38	2.77	144446380.32	52.02	0.00032
$P_{10,3}$	118822709.42	8.35	118832454.73	84.77	0.00820
$P_{10,4}$	99542103.52	73.53	99687681.88	113.88	0.14625
$P_{20,2}$	161108867.00	31.34	161110052.87	398.10	0.00074
$P_{20,3}$	140161536.81	13295.75	140207680.84	626.52	0.03292
$P_{25,2}$	165391046.18	311.57	165392914.22	893.47	0.00113

We also used a bigger real-life dataset representing the Turkish intercity transportation network, which contains the pairwise distances (in kilometers) between 81 provincial cities. This dataset was originally compiled and utilized in previous hub location studies [14]. The dataset provides travel distances, travel times, flows, and costs between the cities. Since our proposed MISOCP model requires planar coordinates for spokes to find coordinates of hubs, and the dataset does not include geographic locations, we employed the Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) technique to infer approximate two-dimensional coordinates for each city. MDS is a dimensionality reduction technique that transforms a distance matrix into a set of coordinates [15]. The goal of MDS is to obtain approximate planar coordinates for each city such that the distances between cities approximate the original pairwise distances as closely as possible. These derived coordinates were then used as input to the MISOCP model. We solved the problem with 2 hubs under a 2-hour time limit and obtained a feasible solution whose optimality gap is reported as 56.6%. It should be noted that this solution is obtained in less than 10 minutes, but model continues to prove its optimality. In Figure 1, the location of cities and hubs are given. This real-life implementation demonstrates the practical applicability of the proposed approach. Although optimality is not guaranteed, the model yields high-quality feasible solutions.

Figure 1 Solution obtained for Turkish network (81 cities, 2 hubs) within 2 hours

5 CONCLUSION

Hub location problems are critical in the design of efficient transportation and communication networks. In particular, the planar version of the problem, where hubs can be freely located in continuous space, better captures real-world geographic constraints compared to discrete models. However, the inherent nonlinearity of distance-based costs and assignment decisions makes the problem computationally challenging. Developing exact and scalable formulations for such problems remains as a significant research gap.

In this study, we addressed the PHLP under the uncapacitated and single allocation setting, where hub locations are continuous and transportation costs depend on Euclidean distances. A compact and unified MISOCP formulation was developed by merging distance and assignment decision variables. Second order cone constraints were employed to accurately model the planar geometry of the problem, while Mc-Cormick linearizations were used to handle nonlinear terms arising from product expressions.

The proposed model allows the PHLP to be solved exactly by modern solvers like Gurobi. Computational experiments on benchmark instances derived from the Australian Post dataset demonstrated that the proposed model can find optimal solutions in reasonable time for small sized instances. When compared to a genetic algorithm from the literature, the MISOCP model produced optimal solutions in shorter time, particularly for smaller networks.

For future research, the proposed modeling framework can be enhanced through effective warm-start strategies to accelerate convergence. Furthermore, hybrid heuristic–exact approaches that combine the strengths of mathematical programming and metaheuristic techniques may be developed to improve solution quality and computational efficiency. For instance, PHLGA can be run with a small number of generations and replications to obtain an initial feasible solution, which can then be used as a warm start for the MISOCP formulation. Additionally, decomposition methods can be explored to increase the scalability of the model for solving larger and more complex instances.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TÜBİTAK) [Grant 2224B].

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APPENDIX

Table A1 Nomenclature

Sets, Indices and Parameters	
n	Number of spokes (nodes)
i, j	Indices for spokes; $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$
$a_i = (a_i^1, a_i^2) \in R^2$	Coordinates of spoke i
p	Number of hubs
k, l	Indices for hubs; $k, l \in \{1, \dots, p\}$
w_{ij}	Flow between spoke i and j
$\alpha_c, \alpha_d, \alpha_t$	Collection (spoke to hub), distribution (hub to spoke), transfer (hub to hub) cost per unit flow and unit distance
Decision Variables	
$x_{ik} \in \{0,1\}$	1 if node i is assigned to hub k , 0 otherwise
$y_k = (y_k^1, y_k^2) \in R^2$	Coordinates of hub k
d_{ik}	Euclidean distance between node i and hub k
d_{kl}	Euclidean distance between hub k and hub l
s_{ik}	The continuous variable defined to linearize continuous-binary multiplication, $d_{ik}x_{ik}$
z_{ikjl}	The continuous variable defined to linearize binary-binary multiplication, $x_{ik}x_{jl}$ (by nature it only takes values 0 or 1)
u_{ikjl}	The continuous variable defined to linearize continuous-binary multiplication, $d_{kl}z_{ikjl}$